
How do you imagine a Circular Economy?

SURVEY REPORT

(November 2022)

IMAGINE
CIRCULARITY

This report was written by a team from the Copernicus Institute of Sustainable Development, Faculty of Geosciences, Utrecht University presenting the results of the “Imagine Circularity” global circular economy perception survey developed in collaboration with Revolve Circular.

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1. Introduction

Circular Economy (CE) is not a new concept, its origins can be traced back to the 70s, but it has gained increased attention in the last decades. The number of google search results for “circular economy” grew from 23.800 in 2008 to 43,3 million in 2022¹. The CE has thus become a prominent concept in the political and corporate discourses all over the world. The EU launched the First Action Plan on CE in 2015, propelling the concept to the centre stage of the European policy agenda on sustainability (Calisto Friant et al., 2021). The concept is also highly relevant in other countries, especially in China, where it has been part of the national strategy since 2002 (Qi et al., 2016).

The mainstream discourse towards CE was developed in opposition to a so-called “linear economy” as a new economic model (Ghisellini et al., 2016). This model focused on creating an economy with no-waste thanks to multiple value retention loops such as recycle, reuse, reduce, remanufacture, repurpose, refurbish and remine (Reike et al., 2018). However, there are many competing visions of CE promoted by different academics and public, private and non-profit institutions (Korhonen et al., 2018; Lazarevic and Valve, 2017; Repo et al., 2018). Some have praised the economic and environmental opportunities brought about by circular innovations, which could prevent resource shortages, environmental pollution and climate change (Ellen MacArthur Foundation and Material Economics, 2019; Kirchherr et al., 2017). Others have rejected the concept of CE as a “folk tale” that replicates the illusion that we could grow the economy eternally in a finite planet (Giampietro and Funtowicz, 2020; Skene, 2018; Valenzuela and Böhm, 2017). Others still, see the need for a circular society that goes beyond economic growth and considers social justice and political empowerment in order to make sure the benefits and costs of a circularity transition a fairly and democratically shared (Genovese and Pansera, 2020; Jaeger-Erben et al., 2021; Suárez-Eiroa et al., 2021).

All in all, the concept is still in evolution, and it continues to be shaped by academic and societal debates on the topic. Moreover, despite the large enthusiasm for the idea of CE, there is a research and knowledge gap regarding what CE discourse and vision most people prefer. Therefore, to better understand how the variety of actors in society imagines a CE, the first “Global Circular Economy Perception Survey” was launched in April 2021. This survey is a joint initiative from different partners, led by “Revolve Circular” and the “Copernicus Institute of Sustainable Development”. The survey was closed on June 1st, 2022 and received 1150 answers from people in 77 different countries. The goal of this survey is to discover what are the most dominant CE discourses in society and what are the key differences and commonalities among the wide range of survey participants. The survey thus seeks to answer the following research question:

How is circularity perceived by different society actors throughout the world?

¹ Search conducted on August 4th 2022.

2. Methods and Data analysis

The purpose of this report is to provide the findings of the survey that was conducted about the perception of circularity. Previous researchers have conducted specific surveys on CE such as (Walker et al., 2022, 2021) on CE perceptions in different companies and on CE and consumer habits in Finland (Mykkänen and Repo, 2021). However, no survey has yet researched CE perceptions of citizens on a global scale.

The survey includes both qualitative and quantitative questions. The main questions were quantitative (point Likert scale and multiple-choice questions) to allow the statistical analysis and cross-tabulation of a large number of responses. However, some questions were open to allow for a more in-depth understanding of people's perceptions and include aspects and components that the authors might have missed or that cannot be expressed with quantitative questions. The survey was developed and shared using the SurveyHero software. It was available in 18 languages to avoid potential language barriers to participation (including English, French, German, Spanish, Japanese, Portuguese, Russian and Turkish)².

Draft versions of the survey were tested twice with CE practitioners and academics as well as people unfamiliar with CE to gain their feedback and improve the survey. This allowed us to improve the user-friendliness of the survey and the wording and content of questions.

The survey remained open from April 2021 to the 1st of June 2022. The survey yielded 1150 responses (n = 1150). From this sample of 1150 responses, 63% provided a complete review of the questions, meanwhile, the remaining 37% sent an incomplete survey. Survey data was exported from SurveyHero in xlsx format and results were analysed using Excel SPSS and Power BI.

The survey contains three questions related to CE and one last background question. The average time taken to complete the survey was about 25 minutes. The full structure of the survey is included in Appendix.

The survey included 4 sets of questions.

1. How would you prioritise each of the 18 actions in a Circular Economy?

This question was made by regrouping the most prominent Rs (also called action imperatives or value retention options) found in the literature on circularity (including: Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2022; Latouche, 2009; Potting et al., 2017; Vermeulen et al., 2018). The list of 18 Rs is represented in table 1.

² An extended version of the survey with three additional questions was developed in Italian, and about 1472 respondents from Italy. This report does not include these answers but rather the results from the global survey, with respondents from all over the world.

Respondents were asked to assess the importance of each of the 18Rs with a scale from 0 (lowest priority) to 5 (highest priority). Additionally, at the end of this question, as an open question, respondents could add an R or CE action, that they find important for CE and which was missing from the list.

Table 1: 18 R actions

R Action*	Description
Reconceptualise	Redefining concepts of wealth and poverty to end the artificial creation of consumption needs and aspirations.
Recover (energy) (R8)	Capturing energy embodied in waste through incineration or bio-digestion.
Recycle (R7)	Processing waste products to obtain “secondary raw materials”
Redesign	Redesigning products and services to improve their sustainability across their entire life cycle (by enhancing product lifespan, reusability, repairability, modularity, recyclability etc..).
Redistribute	Redistributing power, technology and access to natural resources both between countries and within countries.
Reduce (R1)	Explicit step in product design to use less material per unit of production and to use less toxic materials or chemicals. Also, the conscious decision to reduce your consumption.
Re-evaluate	“Re-evaluating” our values and worldviews away from consumerism, ethnocentrism, anthropocentrism, materialism, productivism and egoism - towards altruism, cooperation, leisure, autonomy and harmonious relation with nature.
Refurbish (R4)	Improving and upgrading certain components of a product or building, to enhance its quality, sustainability, and value. Examples: computers, hotels, offices, airplanes, trains (often called reconditioning or retrofitting).
Refuse (R0)	Avoiding over-consumption of unnecessary products or services (excess clothing, electronics, food, cars, air travel etc.) and rejecting e.g. packaging waste and shopping bags.
Re-localise	"Re-localising" industrial and agricultural production processes.
Remanufacture (R5)	When the full structure of a product is disassembled, checked, cleaned, and, when necessary, replaced or repaired in an industrial process. Some also refer to this as “reprocessing” or “re-assembling”.
Repair (R3)	Bringing back into working order, by repairing items after (minor) defects. This can be done through the producer, or by oneself, also with the help of a network of “repair cafés”.
Replace	Explicit step in product design to substitute polluting and toxic materials or chemicals with safe and sustainable ones or to replace a product by offering the same function with a radically different (e.g. digital) product or service.
Repurpose (R6)	Reusing discarded goods or components adapted for another function such as discarded rubber tyres as fences, old crates as furniture or disused shipping containers as buildings.
Restore	Restoration of natural ecosystem or cultural heritage to their original or improved condition (sometimes called regenerate).
Restructure	Adapting social relations and production systems so they can operate beyond linear growth-dependent structures.
Rethink	Rethinking how value chains are organized and phasing out linear structures, incentives, and mindsets.
Reuse (R2)	Buying/selling second-hand products, reusing packaging, bottles, and bags, or sharing goods such as tools, cars, and other products with one’s community.

*For the 10R that emanate from the R hierarchy developed by Reike et al. (2018) their position in hierarchy is added as a number next to the respective R in this table; however, the survey did not include this number, to avoid influencing survey responses.

2. Which visions are your most and least preferred?

This question asked respondents to choose the vision of CE that appeals the most and the least to them. These visions were based on the typology of circularity discourses developed by Calisto Friant et al. (2020) (see figure 1). The typology distinguished circularity discourses based on two criteria. First, whether they are *optimist* or *sceptical* regarding the possibility that economic growth can be decoupled from environmental degradation fast enough to prevent a socio-ecological collapse. Second, whether discourses are *holistic* by including social justice and political empowerment considerations or *segmented* by focusing on resource efficiency alone. This differentiation leads to 4 broad circularity discourse types: Technocentric Circular Economy (*optimist* and *segmented*), Reformist Circular Society (*optimist* and *holistic*), Transformational Circular Society (*sceptical* and *holistic*), and Fortress Circular Economy (*sceptical* and *segmented*) (see Figure 1 and the appendix for further details).

		Approach to social, economic, environmental and political considerations	
		Holistic	Segmented
Technological innovation and ecological collapse	Optimist	<p>Reformist Circular Society (RCS)</p> <p>" A Circular Economy seeks prosperity and well-being for all within the biophysical boundaries of the earth. It does so through technological breakthroughs and social policies that benefit both humanity and natural ecosystems."</p>	<p>Technocentric Circular Economy (TCE)</p> <p>" A circular economy seeks economic progress and prosperity without negative environmental impacts. It does so through new business models and innovative green technologies that positively transform production and consumption practices "</p>
	Sceptical	<p>Transformational Circular Society (TCS)</p> <p>" A Circular Economy seeks to create a world of solidarity, social harmony, and sufficiency that fairly distributes the biophysical resources of the earth. It does so through a radically democratic transformation of the current socio-political system and a shift away from materialistic, consumerist, utilitarian, ethnocentric and anthropocentric worldviews"</p>	<p>Fortress Circular Economy (FCE)</p> <p>" A circular economy seeks to maintain resource security and secure the biophysical stability of the earth in global conditions where widespread resource scarcity and human overpopulation cannot provide for all. It does so through competitive technologies and business models combined with rationalized resource use and population controls"</p>

Figure 1: Typology of circularity discourses

3. In your vision of a Circular Economy, how relevant do you find the following topics?

This question was developed from a review of academic and practitioner literature on CE to uncover 28 diverse topics related to CE. Like in question 1, respondents were asked to rate each of the 28 topics from 0 (not relevant for CE) to 5 (extremely relevant for CE). Ultimately, as an open question, respondents could add a topic that they find important for CE and which was missing from the list.

4. Optional last question: What would you like to add about your vision of a Circular Economy?

This was an optional question for those that wanted to further expand on their vision of CE and add elements or ideas that they found missing in other questions or that they found important to highlight.

5. Personal Characteristics

Some socioeconomic variables were used as background variables: age, gender, education, sector, nationality, country of residence, and city of residence. Additionally, using the United Nations classification of economic activity, individuals were asked to indicate the sector in which they work and their professional role. Around 41% of participants took the survey using their phones, around 58% used a computer, and only about 1% used a tablet.

3. Results

Once the statistics are carried out the results are reported in three different sections. Section 3.1. looks at the demographic background of respondents. Section 3.2. shows the overall result of each of the 3 main questions on CE. Section 3.3 tabulates these results in relation to participant backgrounds, and Section 3.4 examines the open answers to the optional qualitative questions (question 4, and at the end of questions 1 and 2).

The response rate per question throughout the survey is as follows:

- Question 1: n = 1003 (How would you prioritise each of the 18 actions in a Circular Economy?)
- Question 2: n = 932 (Which visions are your most and least preferred to you and your idea of a Circular Economy?)
- Question 3: n = 881 (In your vision of a Circular Economy, how relevant do you find the following topics? (28 topics)
- Question 4: n = 243 (Optional last question: What would you like to add about your vision of a Circular Economy?)
- Demographic questions: n=842

3.1 Demographic background of respondents

In connection with the overall results, the socio-economic variables were displayed and carefully analyzed: including age, gender, educational level, prior knowledge, nationality, economic sector, and professional role.

In terms of gender, the number of women respondents slightly outweighs the number of men (see figure 2). Regarding age, around 52% of respondents are 21 to 39 years old, and 36% are 40 to 59 years old. This is significantly higher than their respective numbers in the global population. On the other hand, there is an under-representation of people under 20 and over 60.

Figure 2: Responses by gender, n =843

Figure 3: Responses by Age Range, n= 842

Figure 4: Responses by Nationality, n = 842

Table 2: Responses by Nationality, n= 841

Nationality	Number	%
Bulgaria	116	14.2%
Greece	80	9.5%
Japan	48	5.7%
Germany	43	5.1%
Kosovo	40	4.8%
United Kingdom	38	4.5%
Netherlands	35	4.2%
Poland	32	3.8%
Italy	28	3.3%
Albania	26	3.1%
Other	352	41.9%
TOTAL	841	100.0%

Figure 4 and Table 2 present the nationality of respondents. As shown in figure 5, a large majority of participants are from Europe, while Oceanian and African participants are rather under-represented.

Figure 5: Responses by Continent, n = 841

In terms of education, figure 6 shows that about 90% of surveyed people hold a university degree at either the bachelor, master, or doctoral level. They thus have a high level of education compared to the general population.

Figure 6: Responses by Level of Education, n = 842

With respect to prior knowledge about CE, most respondents have at least 3 years of knowledge on CE (59%) and 31% of respondents have more than 5 years of knowledge. Most respondents are thus quite familiar with the concept of CE.

Figure 7: Answer to the question: "How long have you known about the Circular Economy?", n = 842

Table 3: Responses per Sector, n = 841

Sector	Number	%
Professional, Scientific and Technical Activities	141	16.8%
Education	124	14.7%
Information and Communication	100	11.9%
Other	95	11.3%
Manufacturing	60	7.1%
Other Service Activities	58	6.9%
Financial and Insurance Activities	39	4.6%
Water Supply; Sewerage, Waste Management and Remediation Activities	26	3.1%
Construction	25	3.0%
Human Health and Social Work Activities	25	3.0%
Public Administration and Defence; Compulsory Social Security	25	3.0%
Agriculture, Forestry and Fishing	24	2.9%
Arts, Entertainment and Recreation	21	2.5%
Wholesale and Retail Trade; Repair of Motor Vehicles and Motorcycles	17	2.0%
Administrative and Support Service Activities	16	1.9%
Activities of Extraterritorial Organisations and Bodies	11	1.3%
Electricity, Gas, Steam and Air Conditioning Supply	9	1.1%
Transportation and Storage	9	1.1%
Accommodation and Food Service Activities	6	0.7%
Real Estate Activities	6	0.7%
Mining and Quarrying	4	0.5%
TOTAL	841	100.0%

Figure 8: Responses per Professional Role, n = 841

Table 3 shows that most respondents work in the tertiary economic sector (around 77%), especially in technical scientific activities, education, information and communication, public administration, finance, and insurance. Some respondents work in the secondary economic sector (about 10%) including manufacturing and construction. Very few are in the primary sector (around 3.4%) including agriculture and mining. Figure 8 shows a rather comprehensive and diverse list of professional roles from junior management to consultants as well as students. There is a notable under-representation of retired and unemployed people (representing just 2% of respondents in total).

All in all, it seems like the survey was answered in greater proportion by highly educated European people from 30 to 50 years old, in their mid-professional career, with a rather good prior knowledge of CE. It is a rather specific group of somewhat expert academics and practitioners on the topic, rather than a representative sample of the general population.

3.2. Overall results for each question

The first question asked participants to prioritise 18 R-actions with a score of 0-lowest priority to 5-highest priority. The results showing the mean response to each R-action are represented in table 4. The Rs that were, on average, placed in higher priority, did not necessarily correlate with the academic R-hierarchy of Reike et al. (2018). For instance, refuse (R0) is ranked 6th, and reuse (R2) is ranked 8th despite being some of the most important Rs in the CE literature. On the other hand, reduce (R1) is ranked second and recover energy (R8) is ranked last, and this follows the academic ranking of the Rs. All in all, there is thus a general preference for high-value retention options like reducing and reusing compared to low-value retention options like incinerating and recycling. Conceptual Rs like rethink, redesign and re-evaluate (our worldviews) are quite highly prioritised. Technical Rs like replace, repair, recycle, and remanufacture are ranked as a medium-high priority and social justice Rs like redistribute, re-localise and reconceptualise are least prioritised. Nonetheless, all Rs have a rather high mean priority score of at least 3.5 (indicating a medium/high priority). This suggests that all actions are found to be important by participants and that no social, technical, conceptual or consumption reduction R is to be left behind when implementing CE actions.

Table 4 also shows how R concepts are prioritized in different parts of the globe. Results for Europe, the rest of the OECD and the Rest of the World (the Global South) are presented in different columns (the ranking of mean scores is presented in parenthesis, cells in red indicate that these Rs were ranked lower compared to global results, while cells in green indicate that they were ranked higher compared to global results). European results are quite similar to global results, except that they found reuse (R2) to be slightly more important than refuse (R0), but still gave a high mean score to both Rs (around 4). On the other hand, refuse (R0) has a relatively higher priority for respondents from the rest of the OECD and the Global South. Those

respondents also ranked recycled as relatively lower in priority compared to Europe, which suggests that they have a stronger focus on consumption reduction than the EU.

Table 4: mean score and ranking of 18 R action in different country-groups*

R concepts	World, n = 1002	Europe, n = 571	Rest of OECD, n = 143	Rest of the World, n = 127
Redesign	4.4 (1)	4.4 (1)	4.6 (1)	4.6 (1)
R1 Reduce	4.3 (2)	4.3 (2)	4.4 (2)	4.4 (3)
Restore	4.1 (3)	4.1 (3)	4.2 (4)	4.3 (4)
Rethink	4.1 (4)	4.1 (6)	4.2 (5)	4.4 (2)
Re-evaluate	4.1 (5)	4.1 (4)	4.2 (6)	4.2 (6)
R0 Refuse	4.0 (6)	4.0 (8)	4.3 (3)	4.3 (5)
R3 Repair	4.0 (7)	4.0 (7)	4.1 (7)	4.1 (8)
R2 Reuse	4.0 (8)	4.1 (5)	4.0 (8)	4.2 (7)
Replace	3.9 (9)	4.0 (10)	4.0 (10)	4.1 (9)
R7 Recycle	3.9 (10)	4.0 (9)	3.7 (15)	3.8 (16)
Restructure	3.9 (11)	3.8 (12)	4.0 (9)	4.1 (10)
R4 Refurbish	3.8 (12)	3.8 (11)	3.9 (11)	4.0 (14)
R5 Remanufacture	3.8 (13)	3.8 (13)	3.8 (12)	4.0 (12)
Reconceptualise	3.8 (14)	3.8 (14)	3.8 (13)	4.0 (13)
Redistribute	3.7 (15)	3.7 (15)	3.6 (17)	4.0 (15)
R6 Repurpose	3.7 (16)	3.7 (16)	3.6 (16)	4.0 (11)
Re-localise	3.6 (17)	3.5 (17)	3.7 (14)	3.8 (18)
R8 Recover (energy)	3.5 (18)	3.5 (18)	3.2 (18)	3.7 (17)

*The ranking of mean scores is presented in parenthesis, cells in shades of red indicate that these Rs were ranked lower compared to world results, while cells in shade of green indicate that they were ranked higher compared to global results (with stronger shades indicating a larger divergence compared to global results).

The second question of the survey is about which circularity vision respondents find most and least appealing. As represented in Figure 9, the discourses found most appealing are Technocentric Circular Economy (TCE) with 33.7 % of the total answers, followed by Transformational Circular Society (TCS) with 29.0%. The least appealing discourses are Fortress Circular Economy (FCE) with 41.8%. An interesting result is that socially inclusive *holistic* discourses like TCS and RCS were slightly preferred (51.6%) compared with *segmented* discourses like FCE and TCE (48.4%), which don't include social justice and political empowerment considerations. On the other hand, *optimist* discourses like RCS and TCE were preferred (56.3%) compared to *sceptical* ones like FCE and TCS (43.7%).

Figure 9: Most and least preferred Visions of Circularity, n= 932

The third question asked participants how relevant they found 28 socio-ecological topics for their visions of a CE (from 0-not relevant to 5-extremely relevant). Table 5 shows that topics related to environmental protection and pollution reduction are found most relevant (like water management, climate change, biodiversity conservation, cleaner production methods, eco-design, reducing consumption and harmony with nature), they are coloured in green in table 5. Socio-political topics are found second most relevant (like education and awareness raising, responsible and ethical consumption, human health and safety, social justice and equity, fair distribution of resources, and democratic citizen participation) they are coloured in blue in table 5. Finally, topics related to economic competitiveness and technological innovation were found least relevant (like sustainable business models, resource security, nature-based innovations, economic prosperity, job creation, economic prosperity etc.), they are coloured in red in table 5. Nonetheless, it is worth noting that the majority of topics have a rather high mean score of at least 3.5 (indicating a medium/high relevance). This suggests that all topics are found to be important by participants and that no social, environmental, or economic consideration should be left behind when implementing CE actions.

Similar to the analysis carried out of 18 R actions, a classification per region of origin of respondents was carried out in Table 5. This reveals some regional differences. For instance, Europeans ranked biodiversity restoration and conservation higher than other regions and ranked sustainable business models lower than other regions. Participants from non-European OECD countries found that a “fair distribution of resource use between rich and poor countries” was less relevant compared to other respondents, yet they still have a rather high mean score of 3.6. Respondents from the Global South placed climate change, reducing consumption and social justice lower than the rest, yet they still gave them high scores (over 4.0 on average) so they are important parts of their CE visions. All in all, variations in mean topic scores are not so strong between different regions, although their relative ranking varies a little.

Table 5: mean score and ranking of 28 socio-ecological topics in different country-groups*

Socio-ecological Topics**	World, n = 881	Europe, n = 571	Rest OECD, n = 143	Rest of the World, n = 127
Sustainable water management	4.5 (1)	4.6 (1)	4.6 (1)	4.5 (2)
Education and awareness raising	4.4 (2)	4.5 (2)	4.5 (4)	4.5 (1)
Fight against climate change	4.4 (3)	4.4 (3)	4.6 (2)	4.4 (10)
Biodiversity conservation and ecosystem restoration	4.4 (4)	4.4 (4)	4.5 (8)	4.4 (7)
Waste management	4.4 (5)	4.4 (6)	4.5 (6)	4.4 (6)
Green and renewable energy	4.4 (6)	4.4 (5)	4.4 (9)	4.5 (3)
Sustainable food	4.3 (7)	4.3 (8)	4.6 (3)	4.4 (8)
Clean production methods and technologies	4.3 (8)	4.3 (7)	4.4 (11)	4.4 (5)
Eco-design of products and services	4.3 (9)	4.3 (11)	4.5 (7)	4.4 (9)
Responsible and ethical consumption	4.3 (10)	4.3 (10)	4.4 (10)	4.4 (11)
Sustainable business models	4.3 (11)	4.2 (12)	4.5 (5)	4.5 (4)
Human health and safety	4.2 (12)	4.3 (9)	4.3 (14)	4.2 (15)
Reducing Consumption	4.2 (13)	4.2 (13)	4.4 (12)	4.2 (16)
Harmony and connection with nature	4.2 (14)	4.1 (15)	4.3 (13)	4.3 (12)
Resource security	4.2 (15)	4.2 (14)	4.1 (15)	4.3 (13)
Drawing inspiration from nature for innovations	4.0 (16)	3.9 (17)	4.0 (18)	4.2 (14)
Social justice and equity	3.9 (17)	3.9 (16)	3.9 (19)	4.0 (21)
Social harmony and community building	3.9 (18)	3.9 (18)	4.0 (17)	4.0 (18)
Sharing and solidarity economies	3.9 (19)	3.9 (19)	4.0 (16)	3.9 (22)
Open-source innovations	3.8 (20)	3.7 (21)	3.9 (21)	4.0 (19)
Fair distribution of resource use between rich and poor countries	3.8 (21)	3.8 (20)	3.6 (25)	3.8 (23)
Economic prosperity and development	3.7 (22)	3.7 (24)	3.9 (20)	4.0 (20)
Job creation	3.7 (23)	3.7 (23)	3.7 (22)	4.0 (17)
Democratic citizen participation	3.7 (24)	3.7 (22)	3.6 (24)	3.8 (24)
Cultural diversity and pluralism	3.6 (25)	3.5 (25)	3.7 (23)	3.7 (26)
Wealth redistribution	3.5 (26)	3.5 (26)	3.4 (27)	3.6 (27)
High-tech innovations such as artificial intelligence, 3D printing and automation	3.3 (27)	3.2 (27)	3.5 (26)	3.7 (25)
Economic competitiveness	3.3 (28)	3.2 (28)	3.3 (28)	3.6 (28)

*The ranking of mean scores is presented in parenthesis, cells in shades of red indicate that these Rs were ranked lower compared to world results, while cells in shade of green indicate that they were ranked higher compared to

global results (with stronger shades indicating a larger divergence compared to global results). **Socio-political topics are coloured in blue, economic and technological topics in red and ecological topics are in green.

3.3. CE discourses and demographic context

In this section, we unpack question 2 on the most preferred CE vision/discourse by analysing how people from different socio-economic contexts answered this question.

Figure 10: CE Discourse preference per Age Range, n = 842

Figure 10 represents CE discourse per age range. Respondents under 30 prefer TCS, while TCE is clearly preferred for those between 30 and 50, and those above 50 are split between TCE, TCS and RCS.

As figure 12 shows, women preferred the TCS vision compared to men. However, their main answers did not vastly differ from the global trend. Non-binary people had the largest difference with global trends, as they overwhelmingly choose TCS as their preferred vision.

Figure 12: CE discourse preference per Gender, n = 843

Figure 13: CE discourse preference per Continent, n = 841

As shown in figure 13, Europe is the only continent in which TCS is the preferred vision. In the rest of the world, TCE is preferred by a rather large margin. Remarkably, TCE and FCE are the first and second preferred options in Africa (with 37.5 % and 28.1% respectively). However, the sample of respondents is rather small in that continent so this might show some bias.

Figure 14: Preferred CE Discourse per Prior Knowledge, n = 842

Figure 14 reveals that respondents with over 5 years of knowledge of CE tend to prefer TCS visions, and clearly favoured holistic and socially inclusive discourses like TCS and RCS. Individuals

without previous knowledge of CE preferred TCS visions (35.8%) followed by FCE (29.9%), which suggests they have more radical views on the topic, yet the sample of respondents in this category is quite small and might thus be unreliable. Respondents with 1 to 5 years of knowledge of CE preferred TCE, although this preference follows a decreasing trend.

Figure 15: Preferred CE Discourse per Education n = 842

Regarding education, figure 15 demonstrates that people with doctoral degrees tend to prefer TCS discourses. Participants with primary schooling on the other hand tend to prefer FCE discourses, but they only represent a sample of 5 respondents, so the data is not reliable.

Figure 16 represents the preferred CE discourses per Sector. Participants in the field of education, service activities, arts and mining seem to prefer the TCS vision, while those in manufacturing, finance, public administration, agriculture, transportation and energy seem to prefer the TCE vision (yet the low number of respondents in most sectors does not allow to make generalisations from these results).

Figure 17 shows the preferred vision based on the respondents' professional roles. Junior management and skilled labourer roles preferred a more radical TCS vision while middle and upper management roles prefer techno-oriented TCE visions. The unemployed, admin staff and support staff preferred the TCE vision. This tends to show a certain level of class division between more technocentric low and upper classes and more progressive middle classes (yet the low number of respondents in some of these roles does not allow us to make generalisations with these results). Consultants, students, and self-employed people are equally split between RCS, TCS and TCE, which a clear certain preference for holistic visions compared to segmented visions amongst this group.

Figure 16: CE discourse preference per Sector n = 841

Figure 17: Preferred CE discourse per Professional Role, n = 841

3.4. Answers to open questions

All open questions were translated to English and interpreted to find the most common comments and responses amongst the hundreds of submissions.

1. First Open Question on the 18Rs: if you think an action is missing, please add and describe it below (n=113)

Most answers did not propose new Rs but rather general actions or topics they found important. Amongst the responses, Re-educate and raising awareness were by far the most common (with 9 people proposing educational actions). This is followed by propositions to encourage sharing and giving activities (with 4 people proposing such actions). Finally, ethical and sustainable consumption was proposed by 3 people and reconnecting to nature was proposed by 2 people. All other responses are quite widespread in terms of topics and propositions going from increasing high-tech investments to keeping oil in the ground. A common theme is a call for

government regulation and a change of political structures to improve governance of CE-related activities (such as better product regulation or changes in taxation practices).

2. Second Open Question on 28 topics: please describe any missing topics or elements you might find important (N=60)

Similar to the results of the previous open question, environmental education, communication, eco-consciousness and cultural transformation is the most highly added topic with 10 people proposing these types of concepts. Empowering local economies and communities was also rather important with 5 responses suggesting actions in this regard. Environmental protection, ecosystem restoration and nature-based solutions were other key topics of importance for 5 respondents. International cooperation and collaboration were found important for 3 respondents, gender equity was mentioned by 2 people and sustainable food systems were mentioned by 2 respondents. Other responses are quite broad and diverse and go from upcycling and dematerialisation to challenging economic growth and valuing indigenous knowledge. As in the Rs, many proposals focus on government actions, especially regulations like supply chain responsibility, and policies to redistribute wealth.

3. Final voluntary question: What would you like to add about your vision of CE? (n=222)

Answers to this question were quite broad and diverse. Some respondents wrote extensively about their vision and others just added a few words or comments. Seven key themes appear from the over 200 responses.

1. Many people stressed the importance of education, communication and awareness raising to change current values towards less materialistic aspirations and increase uptake of CE solutions and approaches and build momentum for transformation, especially in the youth (around 36 respondents).
2. Various participants stressed the idea of CE as a systemic transformation that includes social, political, technical and ecological components in a holistic manner (around 25 respondents).
3. People stressed the importance of a post-growth CE that ditches economic growth as an end and instead seeks to build post-capitalist relations that focus on human and planetary wellbeing (around 19 respondents).
4. Many participants found it key to see humans as parts of nature and therefore sought to protect and regenerate ecosystems and live in harmony within the natural limits of the biosphere (about 15 respondents).
5. People called for synergies and collaborations between civil society, governments, businesses and academics to propel an inclusive and democratic CE transition (about 14 respondents).
6. Many stressed the need to localise social and economic relations to focus on local production and consumption and strengthen community ties to build a bottom-up CE transition (around 10 respondents).

7. The importance of state policies was seen as highly relevant to propelling CE, especially regarding product regulations, tax incentives and support for CE initiatives (9 respondents). S
8. Some respondents reiterated the importance of reducing or limiting population growth (6 respondents).

Beyond those dominant themes, other topics emerged with less support, such as the need for strict monitoring of CE practices and indicators (4 mentions), and the importance of sustainable business models (4 respondents). It is interesting to note that 2 people found a CE transition to be unrealistic considering the current state of the world, and 2 others found that the CE concept was an unnecessary distraction from more important and comprehensive concepts like sustainability and the SDGs. It is also interesting to note that while most people found social and political matters important, 4 people thought it was best not to “politicise” the CE, and to avoid talking of social justice, equity, and redistribution. Rather, they found that a technical and depoliticised vision of CE would be less confrontational, gain more widespread support and avoid ostracising business actors and incumbent stakeholders. This approach was taken by many governments and NGOs like the Ellen MacArthur foundation and perhaps accounts for the impressive rise in popularity of the concept in mainstream debates during the last decade. However, this approach also risks making the CE socially irrelevant and political illegitimate faced with the increasing global inequalities in wealth and the many disparities in the costs and impacts of the CE transition that can already be witnessed (Hobson and Lynch, 2016).

4. Conclusions

Other research on CE has found that the dominant discourse of CE in public and private institutions is TCE (Berry et al., 2021; Calisto Friant et al., 2022b, 2022a, 2021; Campbell-Johnston et al., 2020; Melles, 2021; Ortega Alvarado et al., 2021; Palm et al., 2021). The findings of this survey suggest, that this TCE vision of CE also has some support from respondents, however, participants have a much more diverse outlook on CE. *Holistic* discourses that include social justice and political empowerment considerations like TCS and RCS were in fact preferred compared to *segmented* discourses, which focus on resource efficiency like TCE and FCE (51.6% vs 48.4%, see figure 9). Moreover, various social Rs and topics were considered important for respondents such as “social justice and equity”, “sharing and solidarity economies”, and “fair distribution of resource use between rich and poor countries” (see tables 4 and 5). Consumption reduction and reduce and refuse action imperatives were also considered to be highly important (see tables 4 and 5). It is thus quite clear that people value more socially inclusive, and ecologically systemic approaches to CE compared to the TCE approach that currently dominates policy debates.

Another interesting result is that people with more knowledge of CE and higher levels of education tend to prefer more radical TCS discourses. This reveals that a more progressive and

systemic vision of CE could grow in time as people learn about the concept. These results are in line with those of academics that speak of the need to increase “Circular Literacy” to go beyond technocentric CE solutions and ensure that a CE transition brings about tangible reductions in humanity’s socio-ecological footprint in a socially fair and equitable manner (Zwiers et al., 2020). Efforts to continue increasing circular literacy is hugely important considering the rising impacts of climate breakdown and biodiversity collapse caused by the overconsumption of planetary resources by the wealthiest inhabitants of the Earth (Chancel et al., 2022). More systemic, redistributive, and post-growth circular visions are thus imperative to ensure the wellbeing of current and future generations and prevent the irreversible collapse of the biosphere. Our findings suggest that a more democratic deliberation on CE and greater participation of citizens and scientists in the construction and implementation of CE policies could lead to more transformative actions than what is currently implemented. Indeed, pluralism and diversity in the CE debate is desperately lacking and this is hampering a democratic and free discussion on the shape of the CE transition. It is also currently leading to the imposition of a TCE future that people have not democratically chosen and would most likely not choose if we had an open, educated, and democratic debate on the topic.

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Appendix

Figure A: Typology of circularity discourses

Survey Hero Questionnaire:

1. Which actions do you find most important?

The transformation of a Linear into a more Circular Economy is often understood using different terms starting with "R" or "Re". These "Rs" are the so-called "value retention options", also referred to as the circular economy's "action imperatives".

We present 18 of the most prominent action imperatives - or "Rs" - in alphabetical order. Our first question:

How would you prioritise each of the 18 actions in a Circular Economy?

Please rate each action on a scale from 0- Lowest priority to 5 -Highest priority

- Reconceptualise
Redefining concepts of wealth and poverty to end the artificial creation of consumption needs and aspirations.
- Recover (energy)
Capturing energy embodied in waste through incineration or bio-digestion.
- Recycle
Processing waste products to obtain "secondary raw materials"
- Redesign
Redesigning products and services to improve their sustainability across their entire life cycle (by enhancing product lifespan, reusability, repairability, modularity, recyclability etc..).
- Redistribute
Redistributing power, technology and access to natural resources both between countries and within countries.
- Reduce
Explicit step in product design to use less material per unit of production and to use less toxic materials or chemicals. Also, the conscious decision to reduce your consumption.
- Re-evaluate
"Re-evaluating" our values and worldviews away from consumerism, ethnocentrism, anthropocentrism, materialism, productivism and egoism - towards altruism, cooperation, leisure, autonomy and harmonious relation with nature.
- Refurbish

Improving and upgrading certain components of a product or building, to enhance its quality, sustainability, and value. Examples: computers, hotels, offices, airplanes, trains (often called reconditioning or retrofitting).

- Refuse
Avoiding over-consumption of unnecessary products or services (excess clothing, electronics, food, cars, air travel etc.) and rejecting e.g. packaging waste and shopping bags.
- Re-localise
"Re-localising" industrial and agricultural production processes.
- Remanufacture
When the full structure of a product is disassembled, checked, cleaned, and, when necessary, replaced or repaired in an industrial process. Some also refer to this as "reprocessing" or "re-assembling".
- Repair
Bringing back into working order, by repairing items after (minor) defects. This can be done through the producer, or by oneself, also with the help of a network of "repair cafés".
- Replace
Explicit step in product design to substitute polluting and toxic materials or chemicals with safe and sustainable ones or to replace a product by offering the same function with a radically different (e.g. digital) product or service.
- Repurpose
Reusing discarded goods or components adapted for another function such as discarded rubber tyres as fences, old crates as furniture or disused shipping containers as buildings.
- Restore
Restoration of natural ecosystem or cultural heritage to their original or improved condition (sometimes called regenerate).
- Restructure
Adapting social relations and production systems so they can operate beyond linear growth-dependent structures.
- Rethink
Rethinking how value chains are organized and phasing out linear structures, incentives, and mindsets.
- Reuse
Buying/selling second-hand products, reusing packaging, bottles, and bags, or sharing goods such as tools, cars, and other products with one's community.

1.1. Other actions? If you think an action is missing, please add and describe it below

2. Which visions are you most and least preferred?

In a world that is dominated by Linear Economy, a more Circular Economy may need to be envisioned and imagined before it can come into existence. Multiple organizations have developed definitions, views, and visions of a Circular Economy while there is no commonly agreed-upon definition. Based on our research, we have distinguished 4 main visions which focus on different aspects of circularity.

a) Please choose the vision which appeals the MOST to you and your idea of a Circular Economy

- " A circular economy seeks to maintain resource security and secure the biophysical stability of the earth in global conditions where widespread resource scarcity and human overpopulation cannot provide for all. It does so through competitive technologies and business models combined with rationalized resource use and population controls"
- " A Circular Economy seeks prosperity and well-being for all within the biophysical boundaries of the earth. It does so through technological breakthroughs and social policies that benefit both humanity and natural ecosystems."
- " A circular economy seeks economic progress and prosperity without negative environmental impacts. It does so through new business models and innovative green technologies that positively transform production and consumption practices "
- " A Circular Economy seeks to create a world of solidarity, social harmony, and sufficiency that fairly distributes the biophysical resources of the earth. It does so through a radically democratic transformation of the current socio-political system and a shift away from materialistic, consumerist, utilitarian, ethnocentric and anthropocentric worldviews"

b) Now please choose the vision which appeals the LEAST to you and your idea of a Circular Economy

- " A circular economy seeks to maintain resource security and secure the biophysical stability of the earth in global conditions where widespread resource scarcity and human overpopulation cannot provide for all. It does so through

competitive technologies and business models combined with rationalized resource use and population controls"

- " A Circular Economy seeks prosperity and well-being for all within the biophysical boundaries of the earth. It does so through technological breakthroughs and social policies that benefit both humanity and natural ecosystems."
- " A circular economy seeks economic progress and prosperity without negative environmental impacts. It does so through new business models and innovative green technologies that positively transform production and consumption practices "
- " A Circular Economy seeks to create a world of solidarity, social harmony, and sufficiency that fairly distributes the biophysical resources of the earth. It does so through a radically democratic transformation of the current socio-political system and a shift away from materialistic, consumerist, utilitarian, ethnocentric and anthropocentric worldviews"

3. What makes your Circular Economy?

The last question is about the relationship that a Circular Economy has with key social and environmental topics.

In your vision of a Circular Economy, how relevant do you find the following topics?

Please rate each of the 28 following topics from 0-Not Relevant to 5-Extremely Relevant

- Economic competitiveness
- High-tech innovations such as artificial intelligence, 3D printing and automation
- Wealth redistribution
- Cultural diversity and pluralism
- Democratic citizen participation
- Job creation
- Economic prosperity and development
- Fair distribution of resource use between rich and poor countries
- Open-source innovations
- Sharing and solidarity economies
- Social harmony and community building
- Social justice and equity
- Drawing inspiration from nature for innovations

- Resource security
- Harmony and connection with nature
- Reducing Consumption
- Human health and safety
- Sustainable business models
- Responsible and ethical consumption
- Eco-design of products and services
- Clean production methods and technologies
- Sustainable food
- Green and renewable energy
- Waste management
- Biodiversity conservation and ecosystem restoration
- Fight against climate change
- Education and awareness raising
- Sustainable water management

3.1. Others?

Please describe any missing topics or elements you might find important

4. Optional last question : What would you like to add about your vision of a Circular Economy?

Having answered the three questions so far, we would like to give you the opportunity to add any comments or further elements of your vision of a Circular Economy.

Would you want to add or stress the importance of certain elements, topics or aspects?